

LAG DIRECTORS' VIEWS ON THE LEADER/CLLD APPROACH IN BULGARIA: QUALITATIVE EVIDENCE AND TRIANGULATION WITH SURVEY RESULTS

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Abstract

This article examines the mechanisms that explain why positive attitudes towards the LEADER/CLLD approach in Bulgaria do not automatically translate into actual community engagement. The analysis is based on triangulation of quantitative data from a survey among 321 rural residents and qualitative data from 15 in-depth interviews with LAG directors (2025). The literature already suggests that LEADER functions effectively when local resources are combined with external networks, and when stakeholder participation is substantive rather than formal. Our empirical evidence confirms that Bulgarian citizens generally perceive LEADER positively and do not question its underlying idea or logic. However, participation is uneven and frequently limited. The qualitative interviews reveal that the main barrier is not distrust, but the heavy institutional and administrative burden, which slows down procedures, discourages minor beneficiaries, and dilutes motivation. Directors of LAGs act simultaneously as promoters of the model and translators between communities and the administration. Although critical of current procedures, they remain optimistic about the future of the approach and expect more autonomy and better-designed support instruments in the next programming period. The findings show that the key to unlocking LEADER's potential lies in governance improvements, not in changing the approach's philosophy.

Keywords: LEADER; CLLD; Local Action Groups; rural development; community participation;

Introduction

The LEADER/CLLD approach is one of the most sustainable and recognizable policies for place-based rural development within the European Union. The model's distinctiveness lies in its capacity to turn local communities into active agents—not merely implementers of “top-down” measures, but co-authors of strategies and decisions. Despite this, a persistent tension persists: while the philosophy of LEADER has proven strong and empirical data reveal predominantly positive attitudes toward the model, the actual engagement of the population and beneficiaries remains lower than expected.

This raises an essential analytical question: what are the mechanisms that explain the gap between the positive perceptions of LEADER/CLLD and the actual level of community participation?

The present article provides an explanatory response based on the triangulation of quantitative and qualitative data from the Bulgarian context. Its purpose is to identify the systemic factors that either enable or hinder participation processes and to demonstrate how institutional and organizational characteristics shape the model's practical impact.

The study also contributes to the growing body of evidence on how governance quality shapes the effectiveness of community-led rural development in Central and Eastern Europe.

Methods

The empirical design combines two complementary datasets:

1. A sociological survey conducted in 2025 among 321 residents of rural areas in Bulgaria, aimed at measuring attitudes toward LEADER/CLLD, levels of awareness, and willingness to engage.
2. In-depth qualitative interviews with 15 directors of Local Action Groups, also conducted in 2025.

The interviews were carried out online, following a pre-designed thematic questionnaire that covered: experience and personal assessment of the model; work with beneficiaries; interaction with institutions; identification of key barriers; and ideas for improvement.

The quantitative and qualitative data were not analyzed separately but used within a **triangulation framework**: the survey results were interpreted as surface-level “symptoms,” while the interviews provided insight into the mechanisms underlying those patterns. The interviews were analyzed inductively, with individual codes grouped into four explanatory themes, which are presented in the Results section.

Literature Review

The LEADER/CLLD approach is grounded in the idea that sustainable rural development emerges “from below,” when local communities have the freedom and capacity to define their own strategies and decisions [1]. However, early analyses warned that “community” is not homogeneous and that participation can reproduce local inequalities if strong actors dominate the processes [2,21,22]. This led to a shift toward the neo-endogenous framework, which highlights that while local resources matter, the crucial element is the linkage to external knowledge, markets, networks, and institutions [1].

Further discussions have emphasized that participation under LEADER depends not only on formal institutional inclusion but also on local power relations and the ability to negotiate collective interests [15,16].

European evidence demonstrates that rural innovation arises through diversification, entrepreneurship, and the valorization of territorial specificities [3,23,24,25]. Local Action Groups (LAGs) often act not only as intermediaries for funding but as network coordinators for local agri-food systems [4]. Beyond

economic diversification, LEADER has been conceptualized as a mechanism for social innovation and network-building that transforms traditional governance practices in rural territories [17,18]. Studies also reveal effects on sense of place and social capital, which, although difficult to measure, enhance community cohesion and resilience [5]. Empirical research from Romania confirms the economic impact but stresses that it should be evaluated not only by absorbed funds but also by real added value after subtracting transaction costs [6,7].

Regarding participation processes, the literature identifies specific instruments that ensure genuine stakeholder involvement. *Backcasting*—defining a desirable future and working backwards to the necessary steps—helps translate local needs into operational CLLD strategies [8].

On the “governance tensions” axis, the LAG-municipality dynamic is particularly relevant. Danish evidence identifies three levels of interaction, with the operational one being crucial; excessive municipal dominance, however, compromises the principles of LEADER [9]. In Central and Eastern Europe, “participation” is often formal [10], while in peripheral regions, cultural factors and weak bridging social capital constrain partnerships and limit the model’s effectiveness [11]. Comparative analyses from Southern Europe point to similar challenges, particularly the mismatch between LEADER’s participatory philosophy and administrative implementation frameworks [19,20].

Recent empirical work from Poland and Romania [12–14] confirms that outcomes depend on the capacity, strategy quality, and procedural design of the LAGs. Consequently, analytical focus shifts from “more funding” to “better governance of processes.” Overall, the literature converges on a clear hypothesis: LEADER/CLLD works not because of the funds it allocates, but because of how people work together. When the institutional framework generates excessive administrative or transaction costs, participation declines.

Results

The analysis is based on 15 in-depth interviews with directors of Local Action Groups conducted in 2025. The results are structured into four main thematic blocks that represent explanatory mechanisms behind the quantitative trends identified in the sociological survey among 321 respondents from rural areas.

The qualitative analysis generated four key explanatory themes, each reflecting a distinct dimension of the interaction between local perceptions, participation, and institutional context.

Theme 1: Positive attitudes toward the LEADER/CLLD approach

LAG directors perceive LEADER as the most adequate instrument for local development because it allows genuine adaptation to local specificities and needs. This positive image coincides with the dominant perception within communities. The approach is viewed as fairer, closer to the people, and less competitive than centralized national measures. This explains

why the survey revealed predominantly positive evaluations — both local leaders and the broader population share a favorable image of the approach.

Theme 2: Low actual community engagement despite approval of the LEADER model

Although overall attitudes toward the program are positive, community engagement remains limited. The reason lies not in distrust of the model, but in low awareness, weak civic capital, and territorial disparities. Smaller municipal centers tend to show higher levels of activity, while areas near larger cities are more passive. LAGs make efforts to mobilize people and ideas, but results are sporadic. Hence, the survey finding of “positive attitudes but limited participation” can be explained by the absence of an “internal driver” — people like the idea of LEADER but do not automatically activate themselves to participate.

Theme 3: Bureaucracy and institutional burden turn potential into delay

The main blocking factor that directly undermines effectiveness is the slow and cumbersome administrative procedures, particularly within the State Fund “Agriculture.” These generate chains of delays that discourage beneficiaries, especially smaller ones. When projects are delayed, motivation erodes. Even the directors themselves often act as “translators” between the LEADER philosophy and bureaucratic machinery. Thus, the quantitative pattern of “positive attitudes but criticism of implementation” is explained — the problem is not the approach itself but the way the administration executes it.

Theme 4: Despite difficulties – expectations for evolution and greater autonomy after 2027

Despite the challenges, directors remain optimistic about the future. Their vision is one of greater independence, broader multi-fund financing, and more rational territorial structures. The idea of relocating specific processes to faster institutional units (such as dedicated LAG departments within national agencies) is considered realistic. This also helps explain the persistence of optimism in the survey results — people sense that LAGs are actively trying to push change “upwards.” The directors’ optimism thus serves as a key stabilizing mechanism that sustains trust in the LEADER/CLLD model.

Discussion

The results of the analysis confirm the core logic of the LEADER/CLLD approach: sustainable local development is not imported from above but generated within communities themselves. This is consistent with the concept of *neo-endogenous development*, which places local capacity and social capital at the heart of transformation [26,27]. Both quantitative and qualitative data indicate that the LEADER philosophy enjoys social legitimacy—people recognize it as an appropriate and effective model for rural development.

However, positive attitudes do not automatically translate into active participation. There is a missing link between perceptions and behavior. The interviews reveal that smaller territories tend to display higher levels of engagement, whereas areas near larger cities are marked by passivity. This pattern stems from differences in local capacity, access to information, and the

strength of social networks. Attempts by LAGs to offset these disparities through communication initiatives produce partial but unsustainable effects.

The institutional framework represents another critical dimension. Both beneficiaries and LAGs face a heavy administrative burden, which acts as a systemic bottleneck and limits effectiveness [28]. This is the central structural factor explaining why a positive concept does not always yield full practical outcomes.

A notable empirical finding is the dual role of LAG directors—they are both enthusiastic advocates of the model and intermediaries within a bureaucratic system. This duality turns them into a filter between philosophy and procedure, a finding consistent with empirical research on LEADER implementation across other EU countries.

Despite the challenges, directors maintain a constructive and reform-oriented outlook. There is a shared expectation that, after 2027, LAGs may evolve toward greater operational autonomy—not necessarily as full-paying agencies, but through more flexible, faster, and decentralized functions.

In essence, the system currently operates thanks to people's motivation rather than institutional design. This is a significant analytical conclusion that explains why the LEADER/CLLD model remains resilient *despite* bureaucratic constraints, rather than because of them.

Conclusion

The findings of this study confirm that the LEADER/CLLD approach enjoys strong social legitimacy and is perceived positively by both local communities and territorial leaders. The systemic issue does not lie within the model itself but within the institutional framework through which it is implemented. The primary constraint stems from administrative burden and the slow vertical movement of procedures. As a result, much of the model's potential is dissipated in bureaucratic processes rather than translated into concrete local projects.

The solution does not require a change in the approach's philosophy but rather an improvement in its operational environment. Based on the analysis, three realistic and actionable directions for enhancement can be proposed for the upcoming programming periods:

1. Decentralization of management functions related to project selection and administration.

This does not imply full financial autonomy but rather a meaningful delegation of specific procedures to structures closer to the field, which can process them more efficiently.

2. Flexible advance payments and financial instruments adapted to the scale of beneficiaries.

Small communities operate with limited budgets and cannot afford to “wait for the system.” Timely disbursements help prevent the demotivation of the most active participants.

3. Investment in targeted actions to activate the most minor settlements.

Engagement depends not only on trust or attitudes but also on local capacity and support. Proactive field-

level measures—training, mediation, and micro-support instruments—can unlock potential that would otherwise remain untapped.

These recommendations are consistent with the broader European debate on simplifying CLLD implementation and improving the efficiency of multi-level governance.

Ultimately, the specific strength of LEADER/CLLD lies in its capacity to enable bottom-up development. To fully realize this potential, the institutional framework must be modernized to serve rather than constrain the approach's logic. Encouragingly, LAG directors are already prepared for such a shift; what remains is a matter of managerial decision and political will.

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